

Using Generalized Constraints and Protoforms to deal with adverbs

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Abstract

Computation with information described in natural language (NL) has intrinsic importance because much of human knowledge is described using these languages. Soft Computing approach to NL-Computation concerns with semantic imprecision of natural languages through the use of NL precisiation, generalized constraints and prototypical forms. NLs are basically systems for describing perceptions. NL precisiation consist on expressing the meaning of propositions in NL as generalized constraints. In this paper, adverbs and adjectives in NL propositions are considered as constraints. Thus, generalized constraints are proposed to specify the attribute values associated to nouns by means of adverbs and adjectives. A prototypical form (or *protoform*) is suggested to represent an abstracted summary, a symbolic expression of a noun phrase, involving adverbs, adjectives and nouns. This type of protoform could be used to represent the use of adverbs and adjectives to describe or specify nouns. Then, these cases are considered protoform equivalent.

Keywords: generalized constraints, natural language, protoform, conceptual graph.

1 Introduction

World Wide Web has become the largest available repository in the history of Humankind with billions of Megabytes of information. Most of the knowledge

stored in the Web is written in natural language. Existing search engines are able to retrieve millions of pages in just few seconds, but most of them are not relevant for the user. In order to stop retrieving irrelevant pages, it is necessary to deal with the semantic aspects of the information contained in those pages.

Furthermore, existing search engines are not able to synthesize a query answer from the pieces of information disperse across the Web, that is, they do not have deduction capabilities. There are several obstacles for search engines to be able to do that, but underlying them is the problem of natural language understanding, the basic problem of precisiation of meaning. To deal effectively with those obstacles, Zadeh [24] suggests new tools as: Precisiated Natural Language (PNL), Generalized Constraint Language (GCL) and Protoform Theory (PFT). Computation with information described in natural language, or NL-Computation, for short is of intrinsic importance because much of human knowledge is described in natural language. NL-Computation involves three modules: (a) Precision module; (b) Protoform module; and (c) Computation module. [16].

A prerequisite to mechanization of natural language understanding is precisiation of the meaning of concepts and propositions drawn from a natural language. A proposition in natural language is precisiable if it could be expressed as a generalized constraint [20].

The meaning of a natural language element is precisiated through translation into GCL and is expressed as a generalized constraint. Usually, the natural language element is a proposition, a system of propositions or a concept. And the generalized

constraint may be viewed as a model of meaning [16].

The Protoform module serves as an interface between Precision and Computation modules. Basically, its function is that of abstraction and summarization. Informally, a *protoform*, abbreviation of prototypical form, is an abstracted summary, a concept which is centred on the confluence of abstraction and summarization. More specifically, a protoform is a symbolic expression which defines the deep semantic structure of a construct such as a proposition, command, question, scenario, or a system of such constructs [19]. The Computation module serves to deduce an answer to a query [16].

A Precisiated Natural Language (PNL) is a sub language of precisiable propositions in NL, which primary function is serving as a part of NL which admits precisiation. A proposition, p , in NL is precisiable if it is translatable into a precisiated language, expressed in a mathematically well-defined language. [23].

In PNL a perception is equated to its description in a natural language. The point of departure in PNL is the assumption that the meaning of a proposition, p , in a natural language, NL, may be represented as a generalized constraint. Some of the main components of PNL are: a dictionary from NL to GCL and a dictionary from GCL to PFL [17]. This work could be seen as a first attempt in this direction: to define those dictionaries.

Conceptual graphs [12, 13], based on semantic networks and Peirce's existential graphs, combine the visual advantage of graphical languages and the expressive power of logic. The main motivation of conceptual graphs has been a smooth mapping between logic and natural language. The formal order-sorted logic foundation of conceptual graphs provides a rigorous basis for reasoning processes performed directly on them.

Morton [8] early recognized the advantages of both conceptual graphs and fuzzy logic and combined them into fuzzy conceptual graphs (FCGs). Cao [4] first introduced and studied FCG programs (FCGPs). Continuing that work, Cao [2] establish a sound and complete foundation for FCG programming.

Usually in dictionaries, the meaning of a word is explained by a descriptive definition, a statement which captures the use, the function and the essence

of a term or a concept. Terms, which are included in the meaning definition, constitute a set of keywords associated with the meaning essence. For example, the term "megavitamin_therapy" which meaning in WordNet is "therapy based on a theory that taking very large doses of vitamins will prevent or cure physical or psychological disorders" could be described by the terms contained in the set $B(\text{megavitamin_therapy}) = \{\text{therapy, theory, very large doses, vitamins, prevent, cure, physical, psychological, disorder}\}$. Therefore, those terms should be used to describe what this kind of therapy is, because they constraint the essence of its meaning. It results evident from this example, that a noun phrase as *very large doses* describes better the therapy meaning than just the words *large* or *dose* used independently [10]. It is easy to realize that they constraint the meaning while describing it. In this paper, the role of adverbs and adjectives as noun constraints is analyzed and some ideas about how to manipulate them as generalized constraints are proposed. The role of adjectives as noun constraints by themselves was analyzed in a previous paper [11]. In this paper, we will concentrate in the use of adverbs as adjective modifiers.

2 Introducing adverbs as generalized constraints

A natural language is basically a system for describing perceptions, which are intrinsically imprecise, reflecting the limited human capacity to manage with detailed information [17]. For example, the proposition p : *Monika is very young* express that the age of Monika has a value that could characterize her as being *very young*. Therefore, in spite of her age is not precisely known, we know that it belongs to a set of age values which characterize very young persons (assuming that Monika is a person, of course). That way, the meaning of *very young* is clear, although the precise age is not known.

A prerequisite to the mechanization of natural language understanding is precisiation of the meaning of concepts and propositions drawn from a natural language. A proposition in natural language is precisiable if it could be expressed as a generalized constraint [19].

The concept of a generalized constraint serves as a bridge between linguistics and mathematics by providing a mean of precisiation of propositions and concepts drawn from a natural language [24]. A typical constraint is an expression of the form $X \in C$, where X is the constrained variable and C is the set of values which X is allowed to take. A generalized

constraint, GC, is defined as an expression of the form $GC: X \text{ isr } R$ where X is the constrained variable; R is a constraining relation which, in general, is nonbivalent; and r is an indexing variable which identifies the modality of the constraint, that is, its semantics. R will be referred to as a granular value of X . In the above example, a proposition p : *Monika is very young* in NL is transformed into a generalized constraint $GC(p)$: $Age(Monika) \text{ isr } \textit{very young}$ in GCL, where *very young* is a fuzzy relation representing the degree to which a numerical value of age fits the description of age as *very young* [17].

The main modalities of generalized constraints are [24]:

- Possibilistic ($r = \text{blank}$), where R defines the possible values of X .
- Probabilistic ($r = p$), with R playing the role of the probability distribution of X .
- Veristic ($r = v$), where R plays the role of a verity (truth) distribution of X .
- Usuality ($r = u$), the usuality constraint presupposes that X is a random variable, and that probability of the event $\{X \text{ isu } R\}$ is usually, where usually plays the role of a fuzzy probability which is a fuzzy number
- Random-set ($r = rs$), where X is a fuzzy-set-valued random variable and R is a fuzzy random set.
- Fuzzy-graph ($r = fg$), where X is a function, f and R is a fuzzy graph which constrains f .
- Bimodal ($r = bm$), where R is a bimodal distribution.
- Group ($r = g$), where X is a group variable, $G[A]$, and R is a group constraint on $G[A]$.

GCL serves as a precisiation language in order to express the meaning of propositions, commands as questions expressed in natural languages (NL). But, what is not clear is how to transform a proposition p from NL to a $GC(p)$ in GCL. Therefore, it is necessary to identify methods and algorithms to do this transformation.

Each of the things in the world can be thought of as having a value on each of a set of dimensions such as size, colour, shape, taste, consistency, and other attributes. Each attribute is really a value on some dimension. To distinguish one thing from another, it is necessary to deal with these dimensions.

Lexicons define nouns to designate categories of things, which share a whole set of attributes that distinguish and characterize them. Common nouns represent a strong tendency for particular sets of

values on different dimensions to co-occur. The noun *apple* itself cannot be said to refer to a particular apple; rather it designates a whole category, the category *apple*, which includes many possible individual apples. An apple isn't just an object of a particular shape; it has a characteristic range of sizes, tastes, consistencies, and locations. In other words, the category *apple* is a whole cluster of co-occurring features

In grammatical theory, a *noun phrase* (abbreviated NP) is a phrase whose head is a noun or a pronoun, optionally accompanied by a set of modifiers as adjectives [15]. Noun phrases could be used as the subject or object of a verb. Noun phrases are syntactical units that appear in most sentences expressing a NL constraint applied to nouns and bring information about them.

In a noun phrase as *extremely big apple*, the words *extremely big* define an attribute that characterizes some members of the *apple* category, one possible value on a conceptual dimension, size. The phrase attributes a big size to the apple that is being referred. The word designating the attribute *big* in the example is an *adjective*, while the word *extremely* is an adverb modifying the adjective.

Gasser [5] proposes that an English attributive phrase consisting of an adjective *Adj* designating an attribute *Att* followed by a noun *N* designating a thing category *C* designates the subcategory of *C* whose members have attribute *Att*. Then, if we have the phrase *young Monika*:

This idea could be expressed using Conceptual Graphs (CG) in linear form [13, 7]:

$$[Person: Monika] \rightarrow (Attr) \rightarrow [Young]. \quad (1)$$

In linear notation, concepts have [square brackets] around them, while relations have (parentheses) [9]. *Person* represents a concept type and *Monika* is a referent of this concept type, while *Attr* (attribute) represents a relation. Therefore, *Monika* should appear in the catalogue of individuals declared as a *Person*.

Fuzzy Conceptual Graphs (FCG) extends simple CGs with linguistic labels defined by fuzzy sets as individual markers [8, 3]. For example, the following FCG expresses that *Monika* has an attribute *Age* which has a measure *Young*. *Young* will be the linguistic label of a fuzzy set.

[Person: Monika] → (Attr) → [Age: *] → (Meas) →
[Measure: Young]. (2)

Meas is a relation used to describe an attribute by a quantity. The quantity could be a measure or a degree [13]. There are some underlying problems as: How do we know that Monika is a person? Therefore, we need some contextual information about Monika. Another solution could be to assume it by default.

3 General aspects about adverbs.

Adverbs are a part of speech. They are used to modify any other language part: verbs, adjectives (including numbers), clauses, sentences and other adverbs, except for nouns [15]. Examples:

Mary sings *beautifully*

David is *extremely* clever

Adverbs typically answer such questions as *how?*, *when?*, *where?*, *in what way?*, or *how often?* This function is called the adverbial function, and is realised not just by single words (i.e., adverbs) but by adverbial phrases and adverbial clauses.

Adverbs and adjectives have important characteristics in common [14]:

- Their gradability,
- They have comparative and superlative forms.

The following words, together with their comparative and superlative forms, can be both adverbs and adjectives (see Table 1):

early, far, fast, hard, late

Table 1: Use of late as adjective and adverb

Adjective	Adverb
Robert catches the late train	Robert returns home late.

The comparative *better* and the superlative *best*, as well as some words denoting time intervals (*daily, weekly, monthly*), can also be adverbs or adjectives, depending on how they are used.

Like adjectives, many adverbs are **gradable** [14], which can be modified by *very* or *extremely* (see Table 2):

Table 2: Examples of gradable adverbs

<i>softly</i>	<i>very softly</i>
<i>suddenly</i>	<i>very suddenly</i>
<i>slowly</i>	<i>extremely slowly</i>

The modifying words *very* and *extremely* are themselves adverbs. They are called **degree adverbs** [14] because they specify the degree to which an adjective or another adverb applies. Degree adverbs include *almost, barely, entirely, highly, quite, slightly, totally, and utterly*.

Like adjectives, too, adverbs are inflected in terms of comparison. The comparative and superlative forms of adverbs are sometimes generated by adding *-er* and *-est*.

John works *hard* -- Mary works *harder* -- I work *hardest*

However, the majority of adverbs form the comparative using *more* and the superlative using *most* (see Table 3).

Table 3: Examples of adverbs in comparative form

Adverb	Comparative	Superlative
<i>recently</i>	<i>more recently</i>	<i>most recently</i>
<i>effectively</i>	<i>more effectively</i>	<i>most effectively</i>
<i>frequently</i>	<i>more frequently</i>	<i>most frequently</i>

Adverbs also take comparisons with *as ... as*, *less*, and *least*. In the formation of comparatives and superlatives, some adverbs are irregular (see Table 4)

Table 4: Examples of irregular adverbs

Adverb	Comparative	Superlative
<i>well</i>	<i>better</i>	<i>best</i>
<i>badly</i>	<i>worse</i>	<i>worst</i>
<i>little</i>	<i>less</i>	<i>least</i>
<i>much</i>	<i>more</i>	<i>most</i>

However, an important distinguishing feature is that adverbs do not modify nouns, either attributively or predicatively, as adjectives do.

Many adverbs are formed by adding *-ly* to an adjective (see Table 5). These adverbs are known as ***-ly adverbs*** [14], but also many adjectives also end in *-ly*, including *costly*, *deadly*, *friendly*, *kindly*, *likely*, *lively*, *manly*, and *timely*. In some cases, the suffix *-wise*, like *clockwise*, may be used to derive adverbs from typical nouns.

Table 5: Examples of *-ly* adverbs

Adjective	<i>slow</i>	<i>quick</i>	<i>soft</i>	<i>sudden</i>
Adverb	<i>slowly</i>	<i>quickly</i>	<i>softly</i>	<i>suddenly</i>

Taken as a whole, the adverb class is the most diverse of all the word classes, and its members exhibit a very wide range of forms and functions. Adverbs are considered a part of speech in traditional English grammar, which is derived from Latin grammar.

A logical approach for dividing words into classes relies on recognizing which words can be used in a certain context. For example, some adverbs can be used to modify an entire sentence, whereas others can not.

Following different adverbial functions are described briefly. In the following examples, the adverb is

highlighted in bold, while the word it modifies is shown in italics.

Adverbs as an adjective-modifier typically express something about the degree of the adjective, such as 'very'. Such adverbs are usually called **degree adverbs** [14] for obvious reasons.

- Monika is **very** *young*
- His poetry is **very** *beautiful*.
- The meaning of this passage is **abundantly** *clear*.
- That sign is **hardly** *visible*.

The value expressed by the adjective (i.e. *young*) is transformed by the adverb (i.e. *very*) in a new level, a new value. Using Fuzzy Conceptual Graphs, this sentence can be formulated:

[Person: Monika] → (Attr) → [Young] → (Meas) → [Degree: #very]. (3)

Then, it could be transformed in:

[Person: Monika] → (Attr) → [Age: *] → (Meas) → [Measure: VeryYoung]. (4)

where VeryYoung is the linguistic label of a fuzzy set

In general, it holds that adverbs that end in *-ly* can be modified by the same adverbs that can modify the adjective that results from removing the *-ly* ending.

- He writes **very** *clearly*.
- The sun came out **quite** *suddenly*.
- This species is the **slightly** *slower* growing one.

[Person: #he] ← (Thme) ← [write] → (Manr) → [Clearly] → (Meas) → [Degree: #very]. (5)

In the following examples the adverb modifies a preposition.

- She is standing **very** near the door.

- She's going **directly** to the store.

Adverbs as a verb-modifier convey information about the manner, time, or place of an event or action. They are known collectively as circumstantial adverbs and constitute the most distinctive adverbial classes [14]. They express one of the circumstances relating to an event or action - *how* it happened (manner), *when* it happened (time), or *where* it happened (place). They are often derived from adjectives by using the suffix -ly.

a) **Manner** adverbs tell us *how* an action is or should be performed:

- She sang *loudly* in the bath
- The sky *quickly* grew dark
- They whispered *softly*
- I had to run *fast* to catch the bus

b) **Time** adverbs denote not only specific times but also frequency:

- Robert returns *late*.
- I'll be checking out *tomorrow*
- Give it back, *now!*
- John *rarely* rings any more
- I watch television *sometimes*

c) **Place** adverbs indicate *where*:

- Put the box *there*, on the table
- I've left my gloves *somewhere*

English is a language which prefers a sequence of *subject-verb-object* in its simplest, unmarked declarative statements. A simple *complete sentence* consists of a *subject* and a *predicate*. The subject is typically a *noun phrase*. The predicate is a finite verb phrase.

A noun phrase is a phrase whose head is a noun or a pronoun, optionally accompanied by a set of modifiers [15]. The modifiers may be:

- **Determiners**: articles (*the, a*), demonstratives (*this, that*), numerals (*two, five*, etc.), possessives (*my, their*, etc.), and quantifiers (*some, many*,

etc.); determiners are usually placed before the noun. Most English dictionaries still identify the determiners as adjectives.

- **Adjectives** (*the red ball*); or
- **Complements**, in the form of an adpositional phrase (such as: *the man with a black hat*), or a relative clause (*the books that I bought yesterday*).

Noun phrases could be expanded by adjectival phrases, which are phrases that have an adjective as their head. In turn, adjectives could be expanded by adverbial phrases, which are phrases that have an adverb as their head.

In English, noun phrases can be treated as single grammatical units. A noun phrase can play the role of a verb argument (such as the subject, the object) or the role of the predicate.

Noun phrases can be easily recognized by using a simple parser as the following, written in Prolog using Definite Clause Grammars (DCGs). DCGs constitute an extension of context free grammars that have proven useful for describing natural and formal languages, and that may be conveniently expressed and executed in Prolog. A more complete version could be found in [1]

sentence → nounphrase, verbphrase.

verbphrase → verb, nounphrase.

nounphrase → det(CV), adjnounph(CV).

adjnounph(CV) → noun(CV).

adjnounph(CV) → adjective(CV, Adj),
noun(CV).

adjnounph(CV) → adjective(CV, Adj),
adjective(CV, Adj2),

{Adj \= Adj2}, noun(CV).

This program does not accept repeated adjectives such as in "*big big girl*". It is able also to check whether it is needed an 'an' or an 'a'. Linking this program with a dictionary as WordNet, it is easy to recognize a huge quantity of simple sentences using WordNet terms (nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc.).

When a noun phrase with an attributive adjective is detected as "*the very young girl*", it could be transformed to a predicative adjective form as "*the girl is very young*" and processed as it. In case of a

noun phrase with several adjectives as “*the extremely fascinating big red book*”, it could be processed as if there were several sentences with predicative adjectives: “*the book is extremely fascinating*”, “*the book is big*”, and “*the book is red*”.

Once a noun phrase is detected, the adjective and the noun could be used to determine the characteristic associated to that noun which is being described by the adjective, if there is enough contextual information. For example, the adjective *young* in the sentence *Monika is young* specifies the *age* of *Monika*. But if the sentence was *Monika is tall*, it will specify the *height* of *Monika*. Therefore an auxiliary relation will be needed to establish an association between nouns, adjectives and characteristics; this relation could be expressed by Conceptual Graphs.

[Person: *] → (Attr) → [Age: *] → (Meas) → [Measure: VeryYoung]. (6)

In order to determine the generalized constraint modality *r*, we considered that the usuality modality should be used by default taking into account that the concept of usual value is closer to our intuitive perception of “expected value” than the concept of expected value as it is defined in Probability Theory. [21]. The difference between the concepts of expected and usual values goes to the heart of the difference between precise and imprecise probability theories. The expected value is precisely defined and unique. The usual value is context-dependent and hence is not unique. However, its definition is precise if the natural language predicates which occur in its definition are defined precisely by their membership functions. In this sense, the concept of the usual value has a flexibility that the expected value does not have. Then, a new Prolog fact could be generated as ‘Monika’.age is_u very_young. to represent the generalized constraint.

3 Defining protoforms to manage with adverbs.

Informally, a protoform, A, of an object, B, written as A=PF(B), is an abstracted summary of B. Usually, B is a lexical entity such as a proposition, question, command, scenario, decision problem, etc. More generally, B may be a relation, system, geometrical form or an object of arbitrary complexity. Usually, A is a symbolic expression, but, like B, it may be a complex object. The primary function of PF(B) is to place in evidence the deep semantic structure of B. [Zadeh, Aug-2005].

The prototypical form of the object ‘*Monika*’. *age is very_young* will be *A.B is C*, where A is an abstraction of *Monika*, B is an abstraction of *age*, and C is an abstraction of *very_young*. The same prototypical form could be applied to the objects *Monika is very_intelligent* and *the book is extremely_big*.

Abstraction has levels, just as summarization does. For this reason, an object may have a multiplicity of protoforms. Conversely, many objects may have the same protoform. Such objects are said to be protoform-equivalent. Based on the previous example, we consider that the protoform *A.B is C* could be applied to any noun phrase where the intrinsic semantic structure of that expression corresponds to specifying or describing the value of a subject attribute, including an adverb modifying the adjective. This kind of expression occurs when an adjective is used *attributively* or *predicatively* as in “*the very young Monika*” and “*Monika is very young*”. Therefore, “*the extremely big book*” and “*this woman is incredibly beautiful*” are protoform equivalent with protoform type *A.B is C*.

4 Conclusions

The generalized-constraint-based computational approach to NL-Computation opens the door to a wide ranging enlargement of the role of natural languages in scientific theories [16]. In this paper, adverbs and adjectives in NL propositions are considered generalized constraints as soon as they describe or specify characteristics associated to the noun they describe.

Fuzzy Conceptual Graphs (FCGs) are used to express propositions in natural language, which use adjectives and adverbs. The visual advantage of these graphs and their logic expressiveness shown extremely helpful for defining dictionaries between NL and GCL.

In English, adjectives can be used either *attributively* or *predicatively*. In both cases, a generalized constraint could be used to express how the value of the attribute associated to the noun is conditioned in order to be acceptable. By using simple sentences as the ones presented here a lot of information could be retrieved from documents on the Web.

Furthermore a prototypical form is proposed to represent the deep semantic structure of a noun

phrase, involving adverbs, adjectives and nouns. That way, all of these cases share the same protoform and, therefore, are protoform equivalent.

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